

abbreviation legend

1) raw data Giurgola et al.: the file contains the raw data collected within the study 'MULTISENSORY INTEGRATION AND MOTOR RESONANCE IN THE PRIMARY MOTOR CORTEX' by Serena Giurgola, Emanuele Lo Gerfo, Alessandro Farnè, Alice C. Roy & Nadia Bolognini published in Cortex in 2024
legend:

- sheet 'subjects': ID= participant's code; Sex, M=Male, F=female; Laterality, rx=right-handed; rMT= resting Motor threshold; OO= orbicularis oris
- individual subject's data:
 - CONGRUENCY: 0= unimodal visual or auditory trial, 1=congruent audio-visual, 2= incongruent audio-visual
 - FILE (stimulus): V= visual, A=auditory, AV=audiovisual
 - RISPOSTA ATTESA= number of the correct answer key
 - SLIDE RESP.RESP= participant's given response (number of the key pressed)
 - SLIDE RESP.RT= participant's reaction time
 - TMS= TMS pulse delivery time from syllable onset in millisecond
 - TMS DELAY= Time at which the TMS pulse was actually delivered from the beginning of the syllable in milliseconds
 - MEP OO= motor evoked potentials in mV from the orbicularis oris
 - MEP FDI= motor evoked potentials in mV from the first dorsal interosseus
 - contraction OO= contraction of orbicularis oris before TMS pulse delivery
 - Contraction FDI= contraction of first dorsal interosseous before TMS pulse delivery